

Benzimidazole–galactosides bind selectively to the Galectin-8 N-Terminal domain: Structure-based design and optimisation

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ABSTRACT

We have obtained the X-ray crystal structure of the galectin-8 N-terminal domain (galectin-8N) with a previously reported quinoline–galactoside ligand at a resolution of 1.6 Å. Based on this X-ray structure, a collection of galactosides derivatised at O3 with triazole, benzimidazole, benzothiazole, and benzoxazole moieties were designed and synthesised. This led to the discovery of a 3-O-(N-methyl-benzimidazolymethyl)–galactoside with a K_d of 1.8 μM for galectin-8N, the most potent selective synthetic galectin-8N ligand to date. Molecular dynamics simulations showed that benzimidazole–galactoside derivatives bind the non-conserved amino acid Gln47, accounting for the higher selectivity for galectin-8N. Galectin-8 is a carbohydrate-binding protein that plays a key role in pathological lymphangiogenesis, modulation of the immune system, and autophagy. Thus, the benzimidazole-derivatised galactosides represent promising compounds for studies of the pathological implications of galectin-8, as well as a starting point for the development of anti-tumour and anti-inflammatory therapeutics targeting galectin-8.

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1. Introduction

Galectins are a family of carbohydrate-binding proteins found in most organisms [1]. While all lectins bind (oligo-) saccharides, galectins have a specific affinity for β -galactosides due to the structural and sequence similarity in their carbohydrate recognition domains (CRD) [2]. The family of galectins is divided into three subclasses according to their CRD distribution. The first subclass contains the monomeric galectins, with one CRD that dimerises depending on the concentration and ligand density. The second subclass consists of only the chimera-type galectin-3, which

contains a single CRD that can aggregate with its glycine and proline-rich N-terminal domain [3]. The third subclass comprises the tandem repeat galectins with two different CRDs, at the N- and C-terminals, respectively [1]. Galectin-8 belongs to the subclass of the tandem repeat lectins.

The two distinct CRDs of galectin-8 and the connecting hinge domain are all required for the protein to function [4]. Therefore, blocking the recognition in one CRD is sufficient to hinder the overall functionality of the protein. Although both CRDs bind β -galactosides as found in natural glycans, binding of native oligo-saccharides and glycosphingolipids to the CRD on the N-terminal domain of galectin-8 occurs with a higher affinity [5,6]. For this reason, we aimed to design selective ligands for the galectin-8 N-terminal domain.

Galectins participate in a wide variety of cellular processes such as cell adhesion, migration, proliferation, survival, and differentiation, and are involved in a broad range of pathologies [3,7].

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Galectin-8 promotes VEGF-C mediated lymphangiogenesis, which is involved in many pathological conditions, including tumour metastasis, organ graft rejection, corneal inflammation, and type 2 diabetes [8]. Galectin-8 is upregulated in several cancers, including lung, kidney, bladder, and breast cancer [9]. By modulating the innate and adaptive immune system through the regulation of T-cell homeostasis, galectin-8 is involved in several inflammatory and autoimmune disorders [10,11]. A few reports link the unique functions of galectin-8 to the specificity of the N-terminal CRD [12]. Due to its ability to induce selective autophagy upon recognising damaged intracellular vesicles, galectin-8 also has antibacterial activity [13]. Because of this wide range of functions, selective and high-affinity galectin-8N ligands would be valuable research tools, as well as potential anti-tumour and anti-inflammatory drug candidates. The literature reports a few synthetic galactose-based inhibitors of galectin-8N, including a methyl 3-O-[1-carboxyethyl]- β -D-galactopyranoside [14], galactomalonyl phenyl esters [15], and fused tricyclic galactose–benzene hybrids [16]. The quinoline–galactoside **1** (Fig. 1) is the only galactose-based ligand reported to bind galectin-8N (K_d 110 μ M) with good selectivity over most other galectins [17]. The quinoline–galactoside **2**, lacking the carboxylic acid functionality, had about a 7-fold lower affinity for galectin-8N with a K_d value of 700 μ M. On the other hand, the quinoline–galactoside **3**, bearing α -3,4-dichlorothiophenyl aglycon, binds galectin-3 and galectin-8N with K_d values of 1.2 μ M and 1.5 μ M K_d , respectively [17]. The improved affinity caused by the α -3,4-dichlorophenyl aglycon likely results from a halogen bonding interaction between the 3-chloro substituent and the Gly87 backbone carbonyl, as well as an S– π interaction between the anomeric sulfur and Trp86 [18]. Using quinoline–galactoside **1** as a vantage point, our immediate focus aimed at further improving galectin-8N selectivity over galectin-3. Herein we report the X-ray crystallography of compound **1** with galectin-8N and the use of this structure in the design, synthesis, and evaluation of galectin-8N inhibitors with improved selectivity over other mammalian galectins.

2. Results and discussion

2.1. Structural analysis

The protein used for crystallisation was produced from an N-terminal 6-His-tagged construct where the His-tag was removed using TEV cleavage before final purification. The purified protein starts with Ser4 and ends with Gln158. The three first and the two last amino acids of the construct are not visible in the electron density.

The galectin-8N–lactose complex was obtained by co-crystallisation using 10 mM lactose added to the protein prior to crystallisation, whereas the galectin-8N–**1** complex was obtained by soaking the ligand into galectin-8N–lactose crystals. The crystal structures were determined by X-ray diffraction at resolutions of 1.35 Å for the galectin-8N–lactose complex and 1.6 Å for the galectin-8N–**1** complex (Fig. 2). The binding mode of the methyl β -D-galactopyranoside in compound **1** is identical to the

Fig. 2. (A) The electron density map (green mesh) $2|F_0| - |Fc|$ contoured at 1σ , for compound **1** in complex with galectin-8N (PDB ID: 7AEN; grey cartoon representation). (B) The green dashed lines in the figure reveal the interactions of the carboxy quinoline moiety compound **1** (in sticks: carbon in green, and oxygen in red) with Arg45 and Gln47 (in sticks: carbon in grey, oxygen in red, and nitrogen in blue), accounting for galectin-8N selectivity.

corresponding galactose in the galectin-8N–lactose complex. The HO4 of the methyl β -D-galactopyranoside is involved in a hydrogen-bonding network with Arg45, Arg69, and His65. The HO6 engages in hydrogen bonding interactions with Asn79 and Glu89. The nitrogen atom of the quinoline ring is placed in a favourable position for the electron-rich ring nitrogen to establish an ion–dipole interaction with the guanidinium of Arg45. Furthermore, the

Fig. 1. The structure of the previously reported galectin-8N quinoline–galactoside inhibitors **1–3** [17].

carboxylate moiety of the quinoline is placed in a favourable orientation to establish a water-mediated hydrogen bond with Arg45 (Fig. 2). The ion–dipole interaction and the water-mediated hydrogen bond with Arg45 may account for the higher affinity and selectivity of the quinoline–carboxylate to galectin-8N. The predicted binding mode of compound **1**, previously obtained from molecular dynamics simulations [17], is nearly identical to the binding mode in our galectin-8N–**1** crystal structure.

2.2. Design, synthesis, and binding affinities

For a systematic investigation of the galectin-8N binding pocket, we synthesised a collection of galactosides derivatised at O3 with triazoles carrying substituted benzoic acids (Fig. 3 and Scheme 2). Triazoles are easily accessible through reliable ‘click’ chemistry and are found in several other scaffolds targeting different galectins with high affinity [19].

The triazole scaffold loosely mimics the general scaffold of quinoline **1**, with a benzoic acid attached to a heteroaromatic ring, but with an additional measure of rotational freedom between these two rings (Fig. 3, panel A). A prospective docking approach in the crystal structure of galectin-8–**1** revealed that the triazole nitrogen of compounds **10a–10f** is positioned in proximity to engage in ion–dipole interactions with the guanidinium side chains (Arg45 or Arg69) on either side of the galectin-8N binding site, analogous to the nitrogen in quinoline **1** (Fig. 3, panel B and C). Additionally, the carboxylic acids of **10d** and **10e** are suggested to plausibly overlap that of quinoline **1**, where it engages in binding with the structural water. At the anomeric position of the conserved galactose, both β -5-tolyl and β -O-methyl aglycons have been widely applied in synthetic galactose-based inhibitors of galectins [17]. In this series, both these groups are included as a control for the structure–activity relationship (SAR) of the differently substituted benzoic acid moieties.

The convergent synthesis of triazoles started from a *tert*-butylnitrite-promoted azidotrimethylsilane substitution of aminobenzoic acid derivatives **4a–4c** [20], which yielded aryl azides

5a–5c (Scheme 1). Esterification of the latter in methanol yielded the methyl azidobenzoates **6a–6c**. In parallel, β -D-galactopyranosides **7a** and **7b** were used in a protecting group-free, dibutylstannylene-mediated, 3-O-alkylation to give alkynes **8a** and **8b** (Scheme 2) [21]. In a copper-catalysed alkyne–azide click reaction, azides **6a–6c** were reacted with alkynes **8a** and **8b** to give the methyl benzoates **9a–9f**. Alkaline hydrolysis of esters **9a–9e** produced the respective benzoic acids **10a–10e**. Using the click reaction, benzoic acid **10f** was synthesised directly from azide **5c** and alkyne **8b**. The binding affinities of compounds **9a–9f** and **10a–10f** were determined in a competitive protein-binding fluorescence polarisation assay (Table 1) [22–24].

The binding data presented in Table 1 show that none of the triazole compounds had a higher affinity than the previously discovered quinoline **1**. Nevertheless, the presented data did give us some insight and steered our further design. Among the functionalised triazoles, the most promising structure for binding to galectin-8N was *meta*-benzoic acid **10e** with an affinity of 640 μ M. The *meta*-substituted congeners **9e** and **10b** also had a higher affinity than their *ortho*- and *para*-counterparts. Although the range of binding affinities of compounds **9a–9f** and **10a–10f** on galectin-8N is relatively narrow, the SAR extracted from this series suggests that aromatic structures with *meta*-substituted carboxylic acids are optimal for galectin-8N ligands with a diaromatic scaffold. Our subsequently investigated compound class corroborates this trend.

Scheme 1. Reagents and conditions: (a) TMSN₃, *t*-BuONO, MeCN, 0 °C–rt, 1 h, (81–99%); (b) H₂SO₄, MeOH, 70 °C, overnight (70–92%).

Fig. 3. (A) Visualised rationale for the diaromatic scaffold. (B), (C) Overlay of the docking poses of triazole-benzoic acids **10e** (magenta sticks) and **10d** (cyan sticks) with the experimental binding mode of quinoline **1** (green sticks) in complex with galectin-8N (PDB ID: 7AEN; grey cartoon representation). Hydrogen bonding of **10e** is shown in magenta dashed lines. The hydrogen bonding of the carboxylic acid of quinoline **1** (in green dashed lines) overlaps with the predicted binding of triazole-benzoic acid **10d** (in cyan dashed lines).

Scheme 2. Reagents and conditions: (a) propargyl bromide, K_2CO_3 , $n-Bu_2SnCl_2$, $n-Bu_4NBr$, MeCN, 80 °C, 3 h, (35–86%); (b) Azides **6a–6c**, CuI, DIPEA, MeCN, rt–50 °C, overnight, (59–96%); (c) NaOH, H_2O , MeCN, 50 °C, 30 min, (44–99%).

Table 1

K_d values (μM)^a of compounds **9a–9f** and **10a–10f**.

Compound	Galectin-8N	Galectin-3
7b [24]	6300	4400
Lactose [5,25]	91	231
1 [17]	110 ± 6	380 ± 11
2 [17]	700 ± 41	620 ± 50
9a	1100 ± 250	>2000
9b	1200 ± 280	490 ± 8
9c	940 ± 40	>2000
9d	1400 ± 240	330 ± 75
9e	810 ± 86	510 ± 79
9f	>2000	700 ± 94
10a	1200 ± 180	690 ± 140
10b	760 ± 8	250 ± 40
10c	1500 ± 200	230 ± 49
10d	N.B. ^b	470 ± 70
10e	640 ± 38	500 ± 63
10f	1300 ± 200	190 ± 18
12a	860 ± 91	1500 ± 7
12b	1200 ± 72	1600 ± 180
12c	870 ± 37	510 ± 71
12d	1600 ± 51	620 ± 148
15a	1100 ± 120	N.B. ^b
15b	1600 ± 310	2000 ± 56
15c	1200 ± 210	1600 ± 110
16a	190 ± 24	1400 ± 84
16b	>2000	1100 ± 140
16c	310 ± 26	590 ± 16

^a Results represent the mean ± SEM of $n = 4$ to 8.

^b Non-binding up to the highest tested concentration of 1500 μM .

Benzimidazoles, benzothiazoles, and benzoxazoles are privileged scaffolds in drug discovery [26–28] and were investigated because they fit the diaromatic scaffold presented in Fig. 3, panel A. The heterocyclic rings were hypothesised to engage in a cation– π stacking with Arg45, or form ion–dipole interactions with Arg45 or Arg69, similar to the nitrogen in quinoline **1**. With synthetic accessibility in mind, we initially synthesised the galactosides lacking the carboxylic acid moiety for comparison to the previously reported quinoline **2**.

Scheme 3. Reagents and conditions: (a) i. **7b**, $n-Bu_2SnO$, MeOH, 70 °C, 2 h; ii. $n-Bu_4NBr$, 1,4-dioxane, 85 °C, overnight, (47–64%).

The stannylene-mediated 3-O-alkylation of methyl β -D-galactopyranoside **7b** with alkyl halides **11a–11d** afforded alkylated galactosides **12a–12d** (Scheme 3). It is worth mentioning that the synthesis of compound **12a** did not proceed without the Boc protection of benzimidazole **11a**. The alkylation of methyl β -D-galactopyranoside **7b** with benzimidazole **11a** resulted in the spontaneous deprotection of the Boc group to give benzimidazole **12a**.

Compounds **12a–12d** were evaluated for their binding affinities against galectin-8N and galectin-3 (Table 1). The benzimidazole **12a** and benzothiazole **12c** had binding affinities for galectin-8N comparable to that of the non-functionalised quinoline **2**, while the *N*-methylbenzimidazole **12b** and benzoxazole **12d** had slightly weaker affinities. Benzimidazoles **12a** and **12b** showed selectivity for galectin-8N over galectin-3 and were chosen to investigate the effect of the added carboxylic acid moiety similar to quinoline **2**. The benzimidazole chlorides **14a–14c** were synthesised by 2-chloro-1,1,1-trimethoxyethane condensation from the corresponding 1,2-diamines **13a–13c** [29]. The Boc protection of **14c** afforded the two regioisomers of the benzimidazole **14d**. Alkylation of methyl β -D-galactopyranoside **7b** with the benzimidazoles **14a–14d** via stannylene acetal-mediated 3-O-alkylation afforded the methyl esters **15a–15c** (Scheme 4). The subsequent alkaline hydrolysis produced carboxylic acids **16a–16c**.

Next, the affinities of esters **15a–15c** and their corresponding carboxylic acids **16a–16c** for galectin-8N and galectin-3 were determined (Table 1). The esters **15a–15c** had a similar affinity to the non-functionalised benzimidazole **12b**, with negligible selectivity over galectin-3. In contrast, the carboxylic acids **16a** and **16c** had galectin-8N affinities of 190 μM and 310 μM , respectively; about four-fold higher than their congeners **12a** and **12b**. The carboxylic acid **16b** had a lower binding affinity for galectin-8N and a similar binding affinity for galectin-3 when compared to those of **12a** and **12b**. The benzimidazole **16a** is the most selective monosaccharide ligand for human galectin-8N reported to date with a 7-fold selectivity over galectin-3.

Based on the previously published SAR (Fig. 1), we hypothesised that combining the carboxy-benzimidazole with α -3,4-dichlorothiophenyl aglycon might significantly increase the binding affinity for galectin-8N [17]. A microwave-assisted tin-mediated alkylation of galactosides was adopted to alkylate 3,4-dichlorophenyl α -thiogalactoside **17** with the alkyl chloride **14a** and **14d** to afford compounds **18a** and **18b** [30]. The following alkaline hydrolysis of the methyl esters yielded the carboxy-benzimidazoles **19a** and **19b** (Scheme 5).

The affinities of compounds **19a** and **19b** for galectin-1, -3, -4C (C-terminal), -4N (N-terminal), -7, -8C, -8N, -9C, and -9N are given in Table 2. Compounds **19a** and **19b** achieved over 100-fold gain in binding affinity for galectin-8N compared to the parent compounds **16a** and **16c** with K_d values of 1.8 μM and 2.7 μM , respectively. Furthermore, *N*-methylbenzimidazole **19a** displayed some

Scheme 4. Reagents and conditions: (a) 2-chloro-1,1,1-trimethoxyethane, BF₃·Et₂O, DCM, rt, (92–94%); (b) Boc₂O, DMAP, DMF, rt, (82%); (c) i. **7b**, Bu₂SnO, MeOH, 70 °C, 2h; ii. *n*-Bu₄NBr, 1,4-dioxane, 85 °C, overnight, (65–77%); (d) KOH, EtOH, H₂O, 80 °C, 4–6 h (37–56%).

Scheme 5. Reagents and conditions: (a) **14a** or **14d**, Bu₂SnO, *n*-Bu₄Nl, PhMe, MeCN, MW, 120 °C, 1 h (31–34%); (b) **18a**, KOH, EtOH, H₂O, 80 °C, 6 h (31%). (c) **18b**, LiOH, EtOH, H₂O, 80 °C, overnight (41%).

Table 2

K_d values (μM)^a of compound **19a** and **19b** towards galectins.

	Galectin (N: N-terminal domain, C: C-terminal domain)									
	1	2	3	4 N	4C	7	8N	8C	9N	9C
19a	130 ± 11 a	220 ± 19	5.0 ± 1.1	130 ± 12	120 ± 37	190 ± 33	1.8 ± 0.1	760 ± 160	16 ± 1.5	45 ± 2
19b	87 ± 6.1	100 ± 9	4.1 ± 0.4	78 ± 14	160 ± 12	43 ± 5.5	2.8 ± 0.1	450 ± 23	13 ± 1.2	18 ± 0.7

^a Results represent the mean ± SEM of n = 4 to 8.

selectivity for galectin-8N over galectin-3 and galectin-9N together with about 25–400-fold selectivity over the remaining assayed galectins. The unsubstituted benzimidazole **19b** binds galectin-8N with lower selectivity over galectin-3 and with about 5- and 9-fold selectivity over galectin-9N and galectin-9C, respectively. Hence, the benzimidazole *N*-methyl group in **19a** apparently induced a small selectivity for galectin-8N over galectin-3.

Taken together, the previously published quinoline–galactoside ligands [17], the structural analysis of **1** in complex with galectin-8N (Fig. 2), and the affinity data presented here show that galactosides derivatised at O3 with fused bicyclic heterocycles carrying a carboxylic acid moiety enhance galectin-8N affinity. A further comparison of the benzimidazoles **16a** and **16c** with **19a** and **19b** confirms earlier observations that an α -anomeric 3,4-dichlorothiophenyl aglycon improves the binding affinity for galectin-8N by two orders of magnitude. However, the 3,4-dichlorothiophenyl aglycon also improves affinity for galectin-3 and thus reduces the selectivity.

2.3. Molecular modelling

Molecular dynamics simulations were performed to understand the selectivity of the benzimidazole–galactosides for galectin-8N. In all simulations, the *N*-methyl benzimidazole ring stacked with Arg45 in galectin-8N or the corresponding Arg144 in galectin-3 (Fig. 4). The main difference between the binding modes in the two galectin CRDs is the placement of the benzimidazole. In galectin-8N, both benzimidazoles **16a** and **19a** point the *N*-methyl group towards the galactose O2, whereas in galectin-3 the *N*-methyl group, and consequently the carboxylic acid, point away from the O2. As a result, the basic nitrogen of the benzimidazole can form a hydrogen bond with Gln47 of galectin-8N, which is not possible with the corresponding Ala146 or Asp148 in galectin-3. The *N*-methyl group of a bound benzimidazole-based inhibitor covers and thus shields the arginine side chain from bulk water, which may partly explain the binding affinity of compound **16b**. As for compound **19a**, a halogen bond was indicated by the close

Fig. 4. (A), (B) Molecular dynamics simulation snapshots of representative low-energy conformations of **16a** (in yellow sticks) in complex with galectin-8N and galectin-3, respectively. (C), (D) Molecular dynamics simulation snapshots of representative low-energy conformations of **19a** (in teal sticks) in complex with galectin-8N and galectin-3, respectively. Hydrogen bonding is shown in corresponding dashed lines.

distance and straight angle between the 3-chloro substituent and the backbone carbonyl oxygen of Gly87 in galectin-8N, and Gly182 in galectin-3, respectively (Fig. 4, panels C and D). This halogen bonding is consistent with previous findings [18]. The carboxylate moiety of the benzimidazole was placed in a favourable position to establish a water-mediated hydrogen bond with Gly142 in galectin-8N (Fig. 4, panel A). The binding of the nitrogen lone pair of the benzimidazole to the non-conserved Gln47 likely contributes the higher selectivity of the benzimidazole–galactosides compared to the quinoline–galactosides.

3. Conclusion

We have crystallised the quinoline–galactoside **1** with galectin-8N and unravelled the interactions accounting for the selectivity for galectin-8N. This crystal structure was used to design heterocycles as quinoline surrogates. The *N*-phenyltriazoles, benzoxazole, and benzothiazole–galactosides showed no direct improvement over the quinoline–galactoside. The benzimidazole and *N*-methyl benzimidazole, however, showed higher selectivity for galectin-8N compared to the original quinoline–galactoside. *N*-methyl benzimidazole **16a** is the most selective monosaccharide galectin-8N ligand to date with 7-fold selectivity over galectin-3. The position of the carboxylic acid proved crucial for both affinity and selectivity for galectin-8N, as evidenced by the comparison of the binding affinities of **16a** and **16b**. The binding affinity of **16a** was greatly enhanced by the introduction of the α -3,4-dichlorothiophenyl moiety, resulting in compound **19a** with a K_d of 1.8 μ M for galectin-8N, while maintaining selectivity over the other galectins. Thus, compound **19a** represents the most potent selective galectin-8N ligand reported to date. Molecular dynamics simulations suggested that benzimidazole galactosides bind the non-conserved amino acid Gln47 in galectin-8N, accounting for the selectivity of

benzimidazole–galactosides. The benzimidazole **19a** represents a promising tool to investigate the biomedical implications of galectin-8 and a steppingstone towards highly selective galectin-8N ligands with potential therapeutic applications.

4. Experimental section

4.1. Competitive fluorescence polarisation experiments

Human galectins-1, -3, -4N, -4C, -7, -8N, -9N, and -9C were expressed and purified as previously described [5,23,31]. Fluorescence polarisation experiments were performed using the PHER-Astar FS plate reader (software version 2.10 R3), and the fluorescence anisotropy of fluorescein tagged probes was measured by excitation at 485 nm and emission at 520 nm. The specific conditions for galectins-1, 3, -4N, -4C, -7, -8N, -9N, and -9C were kept as reported [22,31,32]. The synthesised compounds were dissolved in pure DMSO at 20 mM concentration and diluted in PBS to 3–6 different concentrations, and each concentration was tested in duplicate. The highest inhibitor concentrations tested were 1.5 mM. The average values of K_d and SEM were calculated from 4 to 8 duplicate measurements, showing 10–90% inhibition.

4.2. Protein expression and purification

The clone for galectin-8N was ordered from GenScript (Leiden, the Netherlands). The DNA sequence encoding amino acids 5–158 from human galectin-8 (UniProt entry O00214 isoform 1) was cloned into pET28a with an N-terminal His-tag and a TEV cleavage site. Ser4 in galectin-8N originates from the remaining Ser in the TEV site after cleavage. The plasmid was transformed into *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) R3 and the expression was started by inoculating LB media containing Kanamycin (50 μ g/mL) with an overnight culture.

Cells were grown to OD ~0.6 at 37 °C, induced with 0.5 mM IPTG, and incubated overnight at 18 °C. Cells were harvested by centrifugation, resuspended in lysis/IMAC A buffer (10 mM Tris pH 8, 150 mM NaCl, 0.5 mM TCEP) supplemented with Triton-X, lysozyme, benzonase, and PMSF, and lysed using sonication. Lysed cells were clarified using centrifugation and the supernatant was added to a drop column containing 5 mL α -Lactose Agarose (Sigma Aldrich) and incubated under rotation for 1 h at 4 °C. The column was washed with lysis buffer, and galectin-8N was eluted using 200 mM lactose. Eluted fractions were cleaved using TEV protease overnight at 4 °C and loaded on a 5 mL HisTrap column equilibrated with lysis buffer. The column was washed with 2% IMAC B (10 mM Tris pH 8, 150 mM NaCl, 0.5 mM TCEP, 500 mM imidazole) and uncleaved protein and cleaved His-tag eluted using a linear gradient of 2–50% IMAC B. Flowthrough and wash fractions containing galectin-8N were concentrated and injected on a Superdex S75 16/60 equilibrated with SEC buffer (10 mM Tris pH 8, 150 mM NaCl, 0.5 mM TCEP). The purity was analysed using SDS-PAGE and fractions containing galectin-8N were concentrated to 20 mg/mL.

4.3. X-ray data collection and atomic structure determination

Co-crystals with lactose were formed at 20 °C using 12 mg/mL human galectin-8N in buffer (10 mM Tris/HCl pH 8.0, 150 mM NaCl, 10 mM lactose and 1 mM TCEP) mixed with reservoir 25% (w/v) PEG 2000 monomethylether (MME) in a 1:1 ratio in a 2 μ L hanging drop over 1 mL reservoir in a NEXTAL plate. Crystals were formed in a few days. Before data collection crystals were transferred to a cryo solution (10 mM Tris/HCl pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 10 mM lactose, 25% (w/v) PEG 2000 MME, 20% ethylene glycol (EG) and 1 mM TCEP) and flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen. A co-crystal with lactose grown from a seeded drop with 24% (w/v) PEG 2000 MME in the reservoir was used to soak in compound **1** by transferring crystals in three steps to different soaking drops. First to a 2 μ L drop with glycerol (20% (v/v) glycerol, 25% (w/v) PEG 2000 MME, 10 mM Tris/HCl pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl and 1 mM TCEP), and secondly to a 2 μ L drop with 5 mM compound **1** (10 mM Tris/HCl pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 5 mM compound **1**, 25% (w/v) PEG 2000 MME and 1 mM TCEP), and thirdly to a second drop with 5 mM compound **1** (same composition as before). The incubation times in the first drops were about 15 min and in the third drop about 24 h. Then the crystal was transferred to a cryo solution (10 mM Tris/HCl pH 8.0, 50 mM NaCl, 5 mM compound **1**, 25% (w/v) PEG 2000 MME, 20% ethylene glycol (EG) and 1 mM TCEP) and flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen. 1.35 Å was collected for the galectin-8N - lactose complex at Diamond Light Source, beamline I04. 1.6 Å data was collected for the galectin-8N - compound **1** complex at Swiss Light Source, beamline PXIII. The lactose data set was processed using the Xia2 pipeline [33], and the compound **1** data set using XDS [34] and Aimless [35] programs. Both structures were determined with two molecules in the asymmetric unit in space group P2₁2₁2₁. The structures have been determined using molecular replacement and the Phaser software [36], and the galectin-8N structure with lactose PDB id: 5GZD as a template. The refinement was made using Refmac5 [37], the model building was made in Coot [38], and the models have been analysed using Molprobity [39], (Table S1 in the supporting information).

4.4. Chemistry

All reagents and solvents were dried before use according to standard methods. Commercial reagents were used without further purification. TLC analysis was performed on precoated Merck silica gel 60 F254 plates using UV light and charring solution (H₂SO₄: EtOH 1: 9). Flash column chromatography was performed on SiO₂ purchased from Aldrich (technical grade, 60 Å pore size, 230–400

mesh, 40–63 μ m). Preparative HPLC was performed on an Agilent 1260 Infinity system with a SymmetryPrep C18, 5 μ m, 19 mm \times 100 mm column using a gradient (water with 0.1% formic acid and acetonitrile). Monitoring and collection were based on UV–vis absorbance at 210 and 254 nm. NMR spectra ¹H, ¹³C, 2D COSY, and HMQC were recorded with a Bruker Avance II 400 MHz spectrometer (400 Hz for ¹H, 100 Hz for ¹³C) or a Bruker Avance III 500 MHz spectrometer (500 Hz for ¹H, 125 Hz for ¹³C) at ambient temperature. Chemical shifts are reported in δ parts per million (ppm), with multiplicity (b = broad, s = singlet, d = doublet, t = triplet, q = quartet, quin = quintet, hept = heptet, m = multiplet, app = apparent), coupling constants (in Hz) and integration. High-resolution mass analyses were performed using a Micromass Q-TOF mass spectrometer (ESI). Purities of final compounds were determined by UPLC (Waters Acquity UPLC system, column Waters Acquity CSHC₁₈, 0.5 mL min⁻¹ H₂O–MeCN gradient 5–95% 10 min with 0.1% formic acid). Analytical data are given if the compound is novel or not fully characterised in the literature. All tested compounds were \geq 95% pure according to analytical HPLC analysis.

4.4.1. General method for the preparation of azides **5a–5c**

Aminobenzoic acids **4a–4c** (1 equiv.) were dissolved in acetonitrile (5 mL). At 0 °C, *t*-butyl nitrite (1.5 equiv.) was added, followed by the dropwise addition of trimethylsilyl azide (1.2 equiv.). The reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and stirred for 1 h. The solvent was evaporated *in vacuo*. The crude material was loaded on silica for flash chromatography purification to give azides **5a–5c**. Because of the expected instability of the aromatic azides, these products were stored in the dark at 4 °C. All of the ¹H NMR spectra match the literature [40].

4.4.1.1. *2-Azidobenzoic acid (5a)*. Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **4a** (250 mg, 1.46 mmol), *t*-butyl nitrite (327 μ L, 2.73 mmol, 1.5 equiv.), trimethylsilyl azide (286 μ L, 2.19 mmol 1.2 equiv.). Purification by flash chromatography (1:3, EtOAc/hexane) gave compound **5a** as a solid in 81% yield (240 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.14 (dd, *J* = 7.8, 1.4 Hz, 1H), 7.62 (ddd, *J* = 8.1, 7.4, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 7.31–7.24 (m, 2H).

4.4.1.2. *3-Azidobenzoic acid (5b)*. Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **4b** (200 mg, 1.46 mmol), *t*-butyl nitrite (260 μ L, 2.19 mmol, 1.5 equiv.), trimethylsilyl azide (230 μ L, 1.75 mmol 1.2 equiv.). Purification by flash chromatography (1:20, MeOH/DCM) gave compound **5b** as a solid in 90% yield (215 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.93–7.86 (m, 1H), 7.81–7.75 (m, 1H), 7.47 (t, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 1H), 7.29–7.24 (m, 1H).

4.4.1.3. *4-Azidobenzoic acid (5c)*. Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **4c** (250 mg, 1.46 mmol), *t*-butyl nitrite (327 μ L, 2.73 mmol, 1.5 equiv.), and trimethylsilyl azide (286 μ L, 2.19 mmol 1.2 equiv.). Purification by flash chromatography (1:3, EtOAc/hexane) gave compound **5c** as a solid in 99% yield (296 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.11 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 1H), 7.11 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 1H).

4.4.2. General method for the preparation of methyl benzoates **6a–6c**

Azides **4a–4c** (1 equiv.) were dissolved in dry methanol (2 mL). A catalytic amount of sulfuric acid was added and the mixture heated to 60 °C overnight. After cooling, 5% sodium bicarbonate solution was added to quench the reaction. This mixture was extracted with ethyl acetate. The organic layers were combined, washed with water, dried over Na₂SO₄, and concentrated *in vacuo* to give methyl benzoates **6a–6c**. The reported ¹H NMR matches the

literature [41]. Because of the expected instability of the aromatic azides, these products were stored in the dark at 4 °C.

4.4.2.1. Methyl 2-azidobenzoate (6a). Following the general method, the reaction with **5a** (250 mg, 1.53 mmol) gave compound **6a** as a solid in a 78% yield (214 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.86 (dd, *J* = 7.8, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 7.53 (ddd, *J* = 8.1, 7.4, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 7.26–7.23 (m, 1H), 7.19 (ddd, *J* = 8.5, 7.7, 1.1 Hz, 1H), 3.91 (s, 3H).

4.4.2.2. Methyl 3-azidobenzoate (6b). Following the general method, the reaction with **5b** (270 mg, 1.66 mmol) gave compound **6b** as a solid in a 95% yield (280 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.83–7.79 (m, 1H), 7.72–7.68 (m, 1H), 7.42 (t, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 1H), 7.20 (ddd, *J* = 8.0, 2.4, 1.0 Hz, 1H), 3.93 (s, 3H).

4.4.2.3. Methyl 4-azidobenzoate (6c). Following the general method, the reaction with **5c** (200 mg, 1.23 mmol) gave compound **6c** as a solid in a 74% yield (160 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.08–7.99 (m, 2H), 7.11–7.03 (m, 2H), 3.91 (s, 3H).

4.4.3. Tolylyl 3-O-(prop-2-ynyl)-1-thio-β-D-galactopyranoside (8a)

Tolylyl 1-thio-β-D-galactopyranoside **7a** (1.00 g, 3.49 mmol), *n*-Bu₄NBr (113 mg, 0.35 mmol, 0.1 equiv.), K₂CO₃ (724 mg, 5.24 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) and *n*-Bu₂SnCl₂ (106 mg, 0.35 mmol, 0.1 equiv.), were loaded to a round-bottom flask and put under inert atmosphere. Acetonitrile (10 mL) and DMF (1 mL) were added to give a white suspension. Propargyl bromide solution (0.97 mL, 80 wt% in toluene, 8.73 mmol, 2.5 equiv.) was added and the reaction mixture heated to 80 °C for 3 h. Solvents evaporated *in vacuo*. The mixture was taken up in DCM, washed with HCl_{aq} (0.5 M), purified by flash chromatography (1:20, MeOH/DCM) to give compound **8a** as a white solid in a 49% yield (550 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 7.51–7.44 (m, 2H), 7.19–7.11 (m, 2H), 4.52 (d, *J* = 9.7 Hz, 1H), 4.43 (d, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 2H), 4.20–4.14 (m, 1H), 4.05–3.95 (m, 1H), 3.83 (ddd, *J* = 12.1, 8.4, 4.4 Hz, 1H), 3.77 (td, *J* = 9.4, 2.1 Hz, 1H), 3.65–3.56 (m, 2H), 2.58–2.53 (m, 2H), 2.51 (t, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 1H), 2.36 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 138.50, 133.26, 129.86, 127.85, 88.76, 81.09, 79.52, 78.28, 75.31, 68.69, 67.70, 62.81, 57.71, 21.16. HRMS calcd C₁₆H₂₀O₅S + Na⁺ (M + Na)⁺: 347.0929, found: 347.0922.

4.4.4. Methyl 3-O-(prop-2-ynyl)-β-D-galactopyranoside (8b)

Methyl β-D-galactopyranoside **7b** (205 mg, 1.06 mmol), *n*-Bu₄NBr (34 mg, 0.11 mmol, 0.1 equiv.), K₂CO₃ (219 mg, 1.58 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) and *n*-Bu₂SnCl₂ (32 mg, 0.11 mmol, 0.1 equiv.), were loaded to a round-bottom flask and put under inert atmosphere. Acetonitrile (2 mL) and DMF (0.2 mL) were added to give a white suspension. Propargyl bromide solution (235 μL, 80 wt% in toluene, 2.11 mmol, 2 equiv.) was added and the reaction mixture heated to 80 °C for 3 h. Solvents were evaporated *in vacuo*. The mixture was taken up in DCM, washed with HCl_{aq} (0.5 M), purified by flash chromatography (1:10, MeOH/DCM) to give compound **8a** as a white solid in a 77% yield (190 mg). The ¹H NMR matches the reported literature data [42]. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 4.39 (dd, *J* = 3.4, 2.4 Hz), 4.20 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz), 4.10 (dd, *J* = 3.2, 0.7 Hz), 3.77 (dd, *J* = 6.1, 2.5 Hz), 3.61 (dd, *J* = 9.7, 7.6 Hz), 3.55 (s), 3.54–3.49 (m), 2.91 (t, *J* = 2.4 Hz).

4.4.5. General method for the preparation of methyl benzoate–triazoles 9a–9f, and 10f

Propynyl **8a** or **8b** (1 equiv.), azide **5c**, **6a**, **6b**, or **6c** (1.1 equiv.), and CuI (0.1 equiv.) were charged to a round-bottom flask and taken up in acetonitrile (10 mL). *N,N*-Diisopropylethylamine (DIPEA, 1.1 equiv.) was added, and the reaction mixture stirred overnight at 50 °C. The solvent was removed from the reaction mixture and the crude material loaded on silica for purification by flash chromatography to give triazoles **9a–9f** and **10f**.

4.4.5.1. Tolylyl 3-O-((2-methylcarboxyphenyl)-1,2,3-triazol-4-ylmethyl)-1-thio-β-D-galactopyranoside (9a). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **6a** (150 mg, 0.85 mmol), **8a** (250 mg, 0.77 mmol), CuI (15 mg, 0.08 mmol), and DIPEA (148 μL, 0.85 mmol). Purification by flash chromatography (1:30, MeOH/DCM) gave compound **9a** as a white solid in 61% yield (237 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.03 (dd, *J* = 7.8, 1.5 Hz, 1H), 7.88 (s, 1H), 7.69 (td, *J* = 7.7, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 7.62 (td, *J* = 7.6, 1.3 Hz, 1H), 7.51–7.43 (m, 3H), 7.12 (d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 2H), 5.01 (d, *J* = 13.1 Hz, 1H), 4.92 (d, *J* = 13.1 Hz, 1H), 4.52 (d, *J* = 9.7 Hz, 1H), 4.17–4.12 (m, 1H), 3.97 (ddd, *J* = 10.8, 6.3, 4.2 Hz, 1H), 3.87–3.77 (m, 2H), 3.74 (s, 3H), 3.62–3.55 (m, 2H), 3.13 (s, 1H), 2.92 (d, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 2.38 (dd, *J* = 8.4, 4.4 Hz, 1H), 2.33 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 166.22, 145.64, 136.41, 135.70, 133.44, 131.64, 130.91, 130.82, 130.38, 129.91, 127.57, 126.47, 125.52, 88.64, 82.90, 79.47, 68.68, 65.46, 62.70, 60.90, 52.91, 21.06. HRMS calcd for C₂₄H₂₈O₇N₃S + H⁺ (M + H)⁺: 502.1642, found: 502.1635.

4.4.5.2. Tolylyl 3-O-((3-methylcarboxyphenyl)-1,2,3-triazol-4-ylmethyl)-1-thio-β-D-galactopyranoside (9b). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **6b** (60 mg, 0.34 mmol), **8a** (100 mg, 0.31 mmol), CuI (6 mg, 0.04 mmol), and DIPEA (59 μL, 0.34 mmol). Purification by flash chromatography (1:30, MeOH/DCM) gave compound **9b** as a white solid in 90% yield (140 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.26 (s, 1H), 8.14 (s, 1H), 8.05 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1H), 7.94 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 7.55 (t, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 7.41 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H), 7.06 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 2H), 4.92 (s, 2H), 4.53 (d, *J* = 9.7 Hz, 1H), 4.25 (s, 1H), 3.94 (s, 4H), 3.85 (t, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 2H), 3.77–3.51 (m, 4H), 3.00 (s, 1H), 2.28 (s, 3H), 2.02 (s, 1H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 165.27, 146.31, 136.88, 135.91, 131.26, 131.10, 130.66, 130.34, 129.41, 128.97, 124.37, 122.23, 120.03, 88.03, 82.52, 78.91, 68.17, 64.88, 62.22, 60.36, 52.58, 30.67, 20.55. HRMS calcd for C₂₄H₂₈O₇N₃S + H⁺ (M + H)⁺: 502.1642, found: 502.1639.

4.4.5.3. Tolylyl 3-O-((4-methylcarboxyphenyl)-1,2,3-triazol-4-ylmethyl)-1-thio-β-D-galactopyranoside (9c). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **6c** (150 mg, 0.85 mmol), **8a** (250 mg, 0.77 mmol), CuI (15 mg, 0.08 mmol), and DIPEA (148 μL, 0.85 mmol). Purification by flash chromatography (1:30, MeOH/DCM) gave compound **9c** as a white solid in 61% yield (235 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.24–8.18 (m, 2H), 8.11 (s, 1H), 7.86–7.80 (m, 2H), 7.49–7.43 (m, 2H), 7.13 (d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, 2H), 4.96 (q, *J* = 13.3 Hz, 2H), 4.50 (d, *J* = 9.7 Hz, 1H), 4.21 (s, 1H), 4.04–3.95 (m, 4H), 3.89–3.78 (m, 2H), 3.59 (dd, *J* = 9.0, 3.2 Hz, 2H), 3.02 (s, 1H), 2.86 (d, *J* = 1.7 Hz, 1H), 2.33 (s, 3H), 2.24 (dd, *J* = 8.4, 4.3 Hz, 1H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 165.82, 146.92, 140.30, 136.41, 131.60, 131.52, 130.83, 129.91, 129.75, 122.70, 120.25, 88.54, 82.99, 79.41, 68.67, 65.38, 62.66, 60.85, 52.91, 52.90, 21.06, 21.05. HRMS calcd for C₂₄H₂₈O₇N₃S + H⁺ (M + H)⁺: 502.1642, found: 502.1638.

4.4.5.4. Methyl 3-O-((2-methylcarboxyphenyl)-1,2,3-triazol-4-ylmethyl)-β-D-galactopyranoside (9d). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **6a** (60 mg, 0.34 mmol), **8b** (63 mg, 0.27 mmol), CuI (5 mg, 0.03 mmol), and DIPEA (47 μL, 0.27 mmol). Purification by flash chromatography (1:5, MeOH/DCM) gave compound **9d** as a off-white solid in 77% yield (86 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.04 (dd, *J* = 7.8, 1.5 Hz, 1H), 7.90 (s, 1H), 7.70 (td, *J* = 7.7, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 7.63 (td, *J* = 7.6, 1.3 Hz, 1H), 7.49 (dd, *J* = 7.8, 1.2 Hz, 1H), 5.03 (d, *J* = 13.1 Hz, 1H), 4.92 (d, *J* = 13.1 Hz, 1H), 4.25 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1H), 4.14 (s, 1H), 4.03–3.96 (m, 1H), 3.92–3.79 (m, 2H), 3.76 (s, 3H), 3.63–3.54 (m, 5H), 3.49 (d, *J* = 5.2 Hz, 2H), 3.25 (d, *J* = 1.7 Hz, 1H), 2.78 (d, *J* = 2.2 Hz, 1H), 2.41 (dd, *J* = 8.3, 4.6 Hz, 1H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 166.22, 145.64, 135.71, 133.44, 130.90, 130.38, 127.59, 126.50, 125.50, 104.84,

81.63, 75.49, 69.99, 65.20, 62.56, 60.81, 56.35, 52.91. HRMS calcd for $C_{18}H_{24}O_7N_3S + H^+$ (M + H)⁺: 410.1558, found: 410.1551.

4.4.5.5. Methyl 3-O-((3-methylcarboxyphenyl)-1,2,3-triazol-4-ylmethyl)-β-D-galactopyranoside (9e). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **6b** (77 mg, 0.47 mmol), **8b** (100 mg, 0.43 mmol), CuI (14 mg, 0.04 mmol), and DIPEA (66 μL, 0.47 mmol). Purification by flash chromatography (1:30, MeOH/DCM) gave compound **9e** as a white solid in 40% yield (68 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 8.69 (s, 1H), 8.50 (t, J = 1.8 Hz, 1H), 8.17–8.12 (m, 2H), 7.74 (t, J = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 4.96 (d, J = 12.6 Hz, 1H), 4.88 (d, J = 12.5 Hz, 1H), 4.20 (d, J = 7.7 Hz, 1H), 4.15 (d, J = 2.5 Hz, 230H), 3.99 (s, 3H), 3.80 (dd, J = 6.1, 3.7 Hz, 2H), 3.68 (dd, J = 9.6, 7.8 Hz, 1H), 3.58–3.52 (m, 4H), 3.49 (dd, J = 9.6, 3.2 Hz, 1H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 164.92, 145.36, 136.41, 131.04, 129.20, 128.47, 123.52, 121.10, 119.88, 103.66, 80.79, 74.25, 69.42, 64.65, 61.33, 60.25, 55.03, 50.85. HRMS calcd for $C_{18}H_{24}O_7N_3S + H^+$ (M + H)⁺: 410.1558, found: 410.1548.

4.4.5.6. Methyl 3-O-((4-methylcarboxyphenyl)-1,2,3-triazol-4-ylmethyl)-β-D-galactopyranoside (9f). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **6c** (47 mg, 0.27 mmol), **8b** (51 mg, 0.22 mmol), CuI (4 mg, 0.02 mmol), and DIPEA (38 μL, 0.22 mmol). Purification by flash chromatography (1:4, MeOH/DCM) gave compound **9f** as a white solid in 59% yield (53 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 8.93 (s, 1H), 8.22–8.14 (m, 2H), 8.08 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 5.07 (d, J = 4.9 Hz, 1H), 4.84 (d, J = 12.6 Hz, 1H), 4.76 (d, J = 12.6 Hz, 1H), 4.65 (t, J = 5.6 Hz, 1H), 4.52 (d, J = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 4.05 (d, J = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 3.96–3.92 (m, 1H), 3.91 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 3H), 3.61–3.42 (m, 3H), 3.39 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 165.81, 146.92, 140.31, 131.51, 129.74, 122.68, 120.25, 104.80, 81.77, 75.44, 70.02, 65.18, 62.58, 60.77, 56.35, 52.89. HRMS calcd for $C_{18}H_{24}O_7N_3S + H^+$ (M + H)⁺: 410.1558, found: 410.1544.

4.4.5.7. Methyl 3-O-((4-carboxyphenyl)-1,2,3-triazol-4-ylmethyl)-β-D-galactopyranoside (10f). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **5c** (71 mg, 0.44 mmol), **8b** (101 mg, 0.43 mmol), CuI (6 mg, 0.04 mmol), and DIPEA (75 μL, 0.43 mmol). Purification by flash chromatography (1:4, MeOH/DCM) gave compound **9f** as a white solid in 44% yield (75 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 8.69 (s, 1H), 8.24 (d, J = 8.7 Hz, 2H), 8.01 (d, J = 8.7 Hz, 2H), 4.98–4.94 (m, 1H), 4.88 (d, J = 12.9 Hz, 1H), 4.20 (d, J = 7.7 Hz, 1H), 4.15 (dd, J = 3.2, 0.9 Hz, 1H), 3.85–3.72 (m, 2H), 3.68 (dd, J = 9.6, 7.7 Hz, 1H), 3.56 (d, J = 2.8 Hz, 3H), 3.55–3.52 (m, 1H), 3.51–3.46 (m, 1H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 146.83, 139.87, 131.61, 122.66, 120.13, 104.79, 81.76, 75.44, 70.02, 65.16, 62.58, 60.77, 56.35. HRMS calcd for $C_{17}H_{22}O_8N_3 + H^+$ (M + H)⁺: 396.1401, found: 396.1399.

4.4.6. General method for the preparation of benzoic acids **10a–10e**

Methyl benzoates **9a–9e** were taken up in acetonitrile (5 mL), NaOH_{aq} (1 mL, 1 M) was added and the reaction mixture heated to 50 °C for 30 min. The reaction mixture was concentrated, water (5 mL) and HCl (1.5 mL, 1 M) was added, and the mixture was extracted with EtOAc (3 × 5 mL). Organic layers were combined, washed with water, and concentrated *in vacuo* to give benzoic acids **10a–10e**.

4.4.6.1. Tollyl 3-O-((2-carboxyphenyl)-1,2,3-triazol-4-ylmethyl)-1-thio-β-D-galactopyranoside (10a). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **9a** (50 mg, 0.10 mmol) to give compound **10a** as a white solid in a 84% yield (41 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 8.48 (s, 1H), 7.91 (dd, J = 7.7, 1.4 Hz, 1H), 7.76 (td, J = 7.7, 1.5 Hz, 1H), 7.67 (td, J = 7.6, 1.2 Hz, 1H), 7.59 (dd, J = 7.8, 1.0 Hz, 1H), 7.37 (d, J = 8.1 Hz, 2H), 7.12 (d, J = 8.0 Hz, 2H), 5.33 (d,

J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 4.80 (dd, J = 27.5, 12.4 Hz, 2H), 4.63 (d, J = 4.8 Hz, 1H), 4.55 (d, J = 9.7 Hz, 1H), 4.01–3.95 (m, 1H), 3.64–3.37 (m, 6H), 2.27 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 167.17, 145.42, 136.41, 135.73, 132.82, 131.64, 130.84, 130.32, 129.91, 126.76, 125.67, 88.60, 83.03, 79.43, 68.66, 65.42, 62.83, 60.90, 21.06. HRMS calcd for $C_{23}H_{26}O_7N_3S + H^+$ (M + H)⁺: 488.1486, found: 488.1485.

4.4.6.2. Tollyl 3-O-((3-carboxyphenyl)-1,2,3-triazol-4-ylmethyl)-1-thio-β-D-galactopyranoside (10b). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **9b** (50 mg, 0.10 mmol) to give compound **10b** as a white solid in a 97% yield (47 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 8.92 (s, 1H), 8.42–8.35 (m, 1H), 8.18–8.11 (m, 1H), 8.06–8.02 (m, 1H), 7.74 (t, J = 7.9 Hz, 1H), 7.37 (d, J = 8.1 Hz, 2H), 7.12 (d, J = 8.0 Hz, 2H), 5.31 (d, J = 6.0 Hz, 1H), 4.85 (d, J = 12.6 Hz, 1H), 4.77 (d, J = 12.6 Hz, 1H), 4.69 (s, 1H), 4.61 (d, J = 4.9 Hz, 1H), 4.55 (d, J = 9.7 Hz, 1H), 4.03–3.98 (m, 1H), 3.62–3.39 (m, 7H), 2.27 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 166.81, 146.77, 137.29, 136.40, 133.11, 131.59, 130.93, 130.84, 129.91, 129.61, 124.46, 122.71, 88.49, 82.98, 79.39, 68.66, 65.32, 62.70, 60.82, 21.06. HRMS calcd for $C_{23}H_{26}O_7N_3S + H^+$ (M + H)⁺: 488.1486, found: 488.1481.

4.4.6.3. Tollyl 3-O-((4-carboxyphenyl)-1,2,3-triazol-4-ylmethyl)-1-thio-β-D-galactopyranoside (10c). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **9c** (50 mg, 0.10 mmol) to give compound **10c** as a white solid in a 76% yield (37 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 8.91 (s, 1H), 8.15 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 8.04 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.37 (d, J = 8.1 Hz, 2H), 7.12 (d, J = 8.0 Hz, 2H), 5.31 (d, J = 5.9 Hz, 1H), 4.81 (dd, J = 30.1, 12.6 Hz, 2H), 4.68 (s, 1H), 4.61 (d, J = 4.8 Hz, 1H), 4.55 (d, J = 9.6 Hz, 1H), 4.00 (s, 1H), 3.63–3.39 (m, 6H), 2.27 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 146.86, 136.41, 131.61, 130.83, 129.91, 122.68, 120.11, 88.54, 82.99, 79.41, 68.67, 65.38, 62.68, 60.85, 21.05. HRMS calcd for $C_{23}H_{26}O_7N_3S + H^+$ (M + H)⁺: 488.1486, found: 488.1483.

4.4.6.4. Methyl 3-O-((2-carboxyphenyl)-1,2,3-triazol-4-ylmethyl)-β-D-galactopyranoside (10d). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **9d** (63 mg, 0.15 mmol) to give compound **10d** as a yellow solid in 97% yield (59 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 13.16 (s), 8.49 (s, 1H), 7.92 (d, J = 6.7 Hz, 1H), 7.77 (td, J = 7.6, 1.1 Hz, 1H), 7.68 (t, J = 7.2 Hz, 1H), 7.60 (d, J = 7.7 Hz, 1H), 5.08 (s, 1H), 4.82 (d, J = 12.4 Hz, 1H), 4.74 (d, J = 12.4 Hz, 1H), 4.53 (d, J = 4.5 Hz, 1H), 4.05 (d, J = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 3.93 (s, 1H), 3.63–3.43 (m, 3H), 3.37–3.29 (m, 4H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 167.12, 145.43, 135.76, 132.86, 130.86, 130.32, 129.19, 126.79, 125.65, 104.82, 81.79, 75.46, 70.00, 65.19, 62.73, 60.82, 56.34. HRMS calcd for $C_{17}H_{22}O_8N_3 + H^+$ (M + H)⁺: 396.1401, found: 396.1399.

4.4.6.5. Methyl 3-O-((3-carboxyphenyl)-1,2,3-triazol-4-ylmethyl)-β-D-galactopyranoside (10e). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **9e** (38 mg, 0.08 mmol) to give compound **10e** as a white solid in a quantitative yield (37 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 13.47 (s, 1H), 13.47 (s, 1H), 8.96 (s, 1H), 8.44–8.37 (m, 1H), 8.17 (dd, J = 8.1, 1.3 Hz, 1H), 8.07–8.01 (m, 1H), 7.75 (t, J = 7.9 Hz, 1H), 5.08 (d, J = 5.0 Hz, 1H), 4.90–4.66 (m, 3H), 4.57 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1H), 4.05 (d, J = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 4.00–3.89 (m, 1H), 3.63–3.41 (m, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 166.75, 146.77, 137.30, 133.04, 130.93, 129.58, 124.50, 122.77, 120.70, 104.76, 81.73, 75.39, 70.01, 64.93, 62.57, 60.56, 56.33. HRMS calcd for $C_{17}H_{22}O_8N_3 + H^+$ (M + H)⁺: 396.1401, found: 396.1397.

4.4.7. General method for the preparation of compounds **12a–12d**

Methyl β-D-galactopyranoside **1** (1 equiv.) and Bu₂SnO (1.1–1.2 equiv.) were dissolved in dry MeOH. The mixture was stirred under reflux conditions for 2 h under N₂ atmosphere. The solvent was evaporated *in vacuo*. The crude was co-evaporated with toluene to

remove any remaining MeOH. The residue was dried under vacuum to give the stannylene acetal intermediate as an amorphous white solid. The dry crude was dissolved in 1,4-dioxane and Bu₄NBr (1.5 equiv.) and the halide **11a–11d** (1.5 equiv.) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred under N₂ atmosphere overnight at 85 °C. The solvent was evaporated *in vacuo*. The crude material was purified by flash chromatography. The compounds were further purified with preparative HPLC prior to galactin binding evaluations.

4.4.7.1. Methyl 3-O-(1H-benzo[d]imidazole-2-ylmethyl)-β-D-galactopyranoside (12a). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **7b** (50 mg, 0.25 mmol), dry MeOH (3 mL), Bu₂SnO (76.9 mg, 0.32 mmol, 1.2 equiv.), anhydrous 1,4-dioxane (3 mL), Bu₄NBr (124.5 mg, 0.38 mmol, 1.5 equiv.), **11a** [43] (70.9 mg, 0.38 mmol, 1.5 equiv.). Compound **12a** was obtained as a white amorphous solid in 60% yield (52.8 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 8.01 (dd, *J* = 8.0, 1.2 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.96 (dd, *J* = 8.3, 1.0 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.53 (td, *J* = 8.1, 7.7, 1.3 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.45 (td, *J* = 7.7, 1.2 Hz, 1H, ArH), 5.17 (ABq, *J* = 14.1, 13.5 Hz, 2H, CH₂C₇H₄N₂), 4.20 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1H, H-1), 4.16 (dd, *J* = 3.3, 1.0 Hz, 1H, H-4), 3.84–3.74 (m, 3H, H-2, H-6a, H-6b), 3.56 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.55–3.51 (m, 2H, H-3, H-5). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 152.23, 135.37, 123.62, 114.12, 104.43, 82.60, 74.92, 70.42, 65.77, 63.94, 60.94, 55.96, 48.24, 48.03, 47.81, 47.60, 47.39, 47.18, 46.96. HRMS calcd for C₁₅H₂₀N₂O₆ + H⁺ (M + H)⁺: 325.1400, found: 325.1399.

4.4.7.2. Methyl 3-O-(1-methyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-2-ylmethyl)-β-D-galactopyranoside (12b). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **1** (50.6 mg, 0.26 mmol), dry MeOH (3 mL), Bu₂SnO (70.8 mg, 0.28 mmol, 1.1 equiv.), anhydrous 1,4-dioxane (3 mL), Bu₄NBr (125.9 mg, 0.39 mmol, 1.5 eq), **11b** (71.4 mg, 0.39 mmol, 1.5 eq). Compound **12b** was obtained as a white amorphous solid in 64% yield (54.4 mg). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 7.71 (q, *J* = 7.4 Hz 2H, ArH), 7.51–7.42 (m, 2H, ArH), 5.17 (q, *J* = 14.1 Hz, 2H, CH₂C₈H₇N₂), 4.19 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H, H-1), 4.17 (d, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 1H, H-4), 3.98 (s, 3H, NCH₃), 3.83–3.70 (m, 3H, H-2, H-6a, H-6b), 3.57–3.52 (m, 6H, H-3, H-5, OCH₃). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 151.16, 135.93, 134.51, 124.30, 123.99, 116.17, 110.69, 104.42, 82.24, 74.88, 70.22, 65.69, 62.55, 60.87, 55.86, 48.03, 47.86, 47.69, 47.52, 47.35, 47.18, 47.01, 29.69. HRMS calcd for C₁₆H₂₂N₂O₆ + H⁺ (M + H)⁺: 339.1551, found: 339.1556.

4.4.7.3. Methyl 3-O-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-ylmethyl)-β-D-galactopyranoside (12c). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **1** (50 mg, 0.25 mmol), dry MeOH (3 mL), Bu₂SnO (76.9 mg, 0.32 mmol, 1.2 equiv.), anhydrous 1,4-dioxane (3 mL), Bu₄NBr (124.5 mg, 0.38 mmol, 1.5 equiv.), **11c** (70.9 mg, 0.38 mmol, 1.5 equiv.). Compound **12c** was obtained as a white amorphous solid in 60% yield (52.8 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 8.01 (dd, *J* = 8.0, 1.2 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.96 (dd, *J* = 8.3, 1.0 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.53 (td, *J* = 8.1, 7.7, 1.3 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.45 (td, *J* = 7.7, 1.2 Hz, 1H, ArH), 5.18 (q, *J* = 14.5 Hz, 2H, CH₂C₇H₄NS), 4.20 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1H, H-1), 4.16 (dd, *J* = 3.3, 1.0 Hz, 1H, H-4), 3.84–3.74 (m, 3H, H-2, H-6a, H-6b), 3.56 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.55–3.51 (m, 2H, H-3, H-5). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 171.62, 152.31, 134.71, 126.01, 125.07, 121.95, 121.70, 104.52, 82.61, 75.03, 70.44, 68.63, 66.01, 61.00, 55.88. HRMS calcd for C₁₅H₁₉NO₆S + H⁺ (M + H)⁺: 342.1011, found: 342.1019.

4.4.7.4. Methyl 3-O-(benzo[d]oxazol-2-ylmethyl)-β-D-galactopyranoside (12d). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **1** (50.2 mg, 0.25 mmol), dry MeOH (3 mL), Bu₂SnO (77.4 mg, 0.31 mmol, 1.2 equiv.), anhydrous 1,4-dioxane (3 mL), Bu₄NBr (125.2 mg, 0.39 mmol, 1.5 equiv.), **11d** (88.2 mg, 0.56 mmol, 2 equiv.). Compound **12c** was obtained as a white amorphous solid in 47% yield (39.1 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 7.75–7.70 (m,

1H, ArH), 7.66–7.63 (m, 1H, ArH), 7.51–7.29 (m, 2H, ArH), 5.06 (q, *J* = 14.9, 2.9 Hz, 2H, CH₂C₇H₄NO), 4.20 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1H, H-1), 4.13 (d, *J* = 2.1 Hz, 1H, H-4), 3.85–3.69 (m, 3H, H-2, H-6a, H-6b), 3.60–3.50 (m, 6H, H-3, H-5, OCH₃). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 150.78, 139.93, 125.44, 124.59, 119.21, 110.58, 104.41, 82.97, 74.97, 70.34, 65.90, 63.92, 60.97, 55.90, 48.25, 48.04, 47.82, 47.61, 47.40, 47.19, 46.97. HRMS calcd for C₁₅H₁₉NO₇ + H⁺ (M + H)⁺: 326.1234, found: 326.1229.

4.4.8. General method for the preparation of compounds **14a–14c**

To a 0 °C solution of 2-chloro-1,1,1-trimethoxyethane (1.5 equiv.) in anhydrous DCM, BF₃·Et₂O (1.1–2 equiv.) was added dropwise followed by the addition of the diamines **13a–13c** (1 equiv.). The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature overnight. The reaction was then quenched by the addition of a saturated aqueous solution of NaHCO₃. The product was extracted by DCM 3 times, and the combined organic phases were washed with brine, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, and the solvent was evaporated *in vacuo* to afford the desired product which was used without further purification.

4.4.8.1. Methyl 2-(chloromethyl)-3-methyl-benzimidazole-5-carboxylate (14a). Following the general procedure, the reaction was performed with 2-chloro-1,1,1-trimethoxyethane (516 mg, 3.34 mmol, 1.5 equiv.), 12 mL anhydrous DCM, **13a** (400.2 mg, 2.22 mmol, 1 equiv.) and BF₃·Et₂O (727.4 mg, 2.46 mmol, 1.1 equiv.). Compound **14a** was obtained as a pale-yellow solid in 94% yield (496.4 mg). The reported ¹H NMR matches the literature [44]. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 8.19 (dd, *J* = 1.7, 0.7 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.94 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 1.6 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.67 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 0.8 Hz, 1H, ArH), 4.98 (s, 2H), 3.95 (d, *J* = 0.6 Hz, 6H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 167.18, 152.82, 144.50, 135.48, 125.29, 123.67, 118.43, 112.18, 51.33, 35.37, 29.45. HRMS calcd for C₁₁H₁₁N₂O₂Cl + H⁺ (M + H)⁺: 239.0587, found: 239.0589.

4.4.8.2. Ethyl 2-(chloromethyl)-3-methyl-benzimidazole-5-carboxylate (14b). Following the general procedure, the reaction was performed with 2-chloro-1,1,1-trimethoxyethane (656 mg, 4.24 mmol, 1.5 equiv.), 7 mL anhydrous DCM, **13b** (551.3 mg, 2.84 mmol, 1 equiv.) and BF₃·Et₂O (916.2 mg, 3.1 mmol, 1.1 equiv.). Compound **14b** was obtained as a pale-yellow solid in 98% yield (705 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 8.32 (s, 1H), 8.03 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 1H), 7.60 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 1H), 4.99 (s, 2H), 4.40 (q, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 2H), 3.95 (s, 3H), 1.43 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 166.86, 152.08, 140.69, 139.03, 125.09, 124.59, 120.78, 109.92, 60.79, 35.46, 29.50, 13.27. HRMS calcd for C₁₂H₁₃ClN₂O₂ + H⁺ (M + H)⁺: 253.0744, found: 253.0746.

4.4.8.3. Methyl 2-(chloromethyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-6-carboxylate (14c). Following the general procedure, the reaction was performed with 2-chloro-1,1,1-trimethoxyethane (1.4 g, 9.03 mmol, 1.5 equiv.), 30 mL anhydrous DCM, **13c** (1 g, 6.02 mmol, 1 equiv.) and BF₃·Et₂O (3.56 mg, 12.04 mmol, 2 equiv.). Compound **14c** was obtained as a pale-yellow solid in 77% yield (1.04 g). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 8.32–8.23 (m, 1H), 7.96 (dd, *J* = 8.6, 1.6 Hz, 1H), 7.62 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 0.6 Hz, 1H), 4.89 (s, 2H), 3.94 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 167.42, 152.66, 124.78, 124.10, 117.54, 114.16, 51.26, 36.66. HRMS calcd for C₁₀H₈N₂O₂Cl + H⁺ (M + H)⁺: 225.0431, found: 225.0435.

4.4.8.4. 1-(tert-butyl) 5-methyl 2-(chloromethyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-1,5-dicarboxylate and 1-(tert-butyl) 6-methyl 2-(chloromethyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-1,6-dicarboxylate (14d). Compound **14c** (500.8 mg, 2.23 mmol), di-*tert*-butyl dicarbonate (550 g, 2.52 mmol, 1.2 equiv.) and anhydrous DMF (8 mL) were

added to an oven dried round flask, then the temperature was adjusted at 5–10 °C. DMAP (20 mg, 0.16 mmol, 0.06 equiv.) was then added and the reaction was stirred at the same temperature for 2 h. After the reaction was stopped, the reaction mixture was diluted with EtOAc (70 mL), washed with aq. NaHCO₃, brine, dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate and EtOAc was then removed *in vacuo*. Purification with flash column chromatography (EtOAc: Heptane 1:2) afforded the desired product **14c** as a pale yellow oil that solidified at room temperature overnight (591 mg, 82% yield). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 8.74 (d, *J* = 1.0 Hz, 1H), 8.46 (d, *J* = 1.0 Hz, 1H), 8.16–8.03 (m, 3H), 7.80 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 1H), 5.09 (d, *J* = 5.9 Hz, 4H), 3.98 (s, 6H), 1.78 (d, *J* = 6.9 Hz, 18H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 166.96, 166.83, 152.87, 151.63, 147.67, 144.93, 141.47, 136.57, 133.09, 127.44, 127.04, 126.87, 126.02, 122.43, 120.16, 117.35, 114.92, 87.23, 52.32, 52.27, 39.40, 39.31, 27.90. HRMS calcd for C₁₅H₁₇N₂O₈Cl + H⁺ (M + H)⁺: 325.0955, found: 325.0953.

4.4.9. General procedure for compounds **15a–15c**

Methyl β-D-galactopyranoside **7b** (1 equiv.) and Bu₂SnO (1.1 equiv.) were dissolved in dry MeOH. The mixture was stirred under reflux conditions for 2 h under N₂ atmosphere. The solvent was evaporated *in vacuo*; the crude was co-evaporated with toluene *in vacuo* to remove any remaining MeOH. The residue was dried under a vacuum to give the intermediate as an amorphous white solid. The dry crude was dissolved in 1,4-dioxane and BuNBr (1.5 equiv.) and the corresponding halide **14a**, **14b**, and **14d** (1.1–1.2 equiv.) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred under N₂ atmosphere overnight at 85 °C. The solvent was evaporated *in vacuo*. The crude material was purified by flash chromatography. The compounds were further purified by preparative HPLC prior to galectin binding assays.

4.4.9.1. Methyl 3-O-((6-methoxycarbonyl)1-methyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-2-ylmethyl)-methoxy)-β-D-galactopyranoside (15a). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **7b** (70.2 mg, 0.36 mmol), dry MeOH (3 mL), Bu₂SnO (98.8 mg, 0.4 mmol, 1.1 equiv.), anhydrous 1,4-dioxane (3 mL), Bu₄NBr (174.4 mg, 0.54 mmol, 1.5 equiv.), **14a** (103.7 mg, 0.43 mmol, 1.2 equiv.). Compound **15a** was obtained as a white amorphous solid in 77% yield (110.92 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 8.23 (s, 1H), 7.97 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 1H), 7.69 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 1H), 5.06 (dd, *J* = 13.1, 6.2 Hz, 2H, CH₂C₁₀H₁₀N₂O₂), 4.17 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 1H, H-1), 4.14 (d, *J* = 3.3 Hz, 1H, H-4), 3.98 (s, 3H, CO₂CH₃), 3.97 (s, 3H, NCH₃), 3.83–3.67 (m, 3H, H-2, H-6a, H-6b), 3.54 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.53–3.48 (m, 1H, H-5), 3.47 (dd, *J* = 9.8, 3.2 Hz, 1H, H-3). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 167.37, 154.55, 144.34, 135.59, 124.83, 123.43, 118.06, 112.00, 104.55, 82.09, 75.04, 70.18, 65.52, 63.25, 61.03, 55.88, 48.24, 48.03, 47.81, 47.60, 47.39, 47.18, 46.96, 29.49. HRMS calcd for C₁₈H₂₄N₂O₈ + H⁺ (M + H)⁺: 397.1611, found: 397.1608.

4.4.9.2. Methyl 3-O-((5-ethoxycarbonyl)1-methyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-2-ylmethyl)-methoxy)-β-D-galactopyranoside (15b). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **7b** (100.5 mg, 0.51 mmol), dry MeOH (3 mL), Bu₂SnO (143 mg, 0.57 mmol, 1.1 equiv.), anhydrous 1,4-dioxane (3 mL), Bu₄NBr (250.1 mg, 0.77 mmol, 1.5 equiv.), **14b** (156 mg, 0.62 mmol, 1.2 equiv.). Compound **15b** was obtained as a white amorphous solid in 65% yield (137.3 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 8.27 (d, *J* = 1.5 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.97 (dd, *J* = 8.6, 1.6 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.53 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 1H, ArH), 5.04 (q, *J* = 13.2, 6.3 Hz, 2H, CH₂C₈H₇N₂), 4.39 (q, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 2H, CO₂CH₂CH₃), 4.18 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1H, H-1), 4.14 (d, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 1H, H-4), 3.93 (s, 3H, NCH₃), 3.84–3.68 (m, 3H, H-2, H-6a, H-6b), 3.54 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.53–3.50 (m, 1H, H-5), 3.46 (dd, *J* = 9.7, 3.2 Hz, 1H, H-3), 1.43 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 3H, CO₂CH₂CH₃). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 167.03, 153.65, 140.57, 139.11, 124.52, 124.08,

120.44, 109.61, 104.56, 82.03, 75.04, 70.18, 65.51, 63.27, 61.04, 60.75, 55.91, 29.53, 13.30. HRMS calcd for C₁₉H₂₆N₂O₈ + H⁺ (M + H)⁺: 411.1767, found: 411.1762.

4.4.9.3. Methyl 3-O-((5-methoxycarbonyl)1H-benzo[d]imidazole-2-ylmethyl)-methoxy)-β-D-galactopyranoside (15c). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **7b** (61.3 mg, 0.31 mmol), dry MeOH (3 mL), Bu₂SnO (86.5 mg, 0.34 mmol, 1.1 equiv.), anhydrous 1,4-dioxane (3 mL), Bu₄NBr (152.2 mg, 0.47 mmol, 1.5 equiv.), **14d** (113.5 mg, 0.35 mmol, 1.1 equiv.). Compound **15c** was obtained as a white amorphous solid in 69% yield (82.9 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 8.27 (d, *J* = 1.5 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.97 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 1.5 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.63 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 1H, ArH), 5.05 (q, *J* = 14.2 Hz, 2H, CH₂C₉H₇N₂O₂), 4.23 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1H, H-1), 4.17 (dd, *J* = 3.3, 1.1 Hz, 1H, H-4), 3.95 (s, 4H, CO₂CH₃), 3.85–3.74 (m, 3H, H-2, H-6a, H-6b), 3.57 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.57–3.54 (m, 1H, H-5), 3.54 (d, *J* = 3.3 Hz, 1H, H-3). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 167.47, 155.27, 123.59, 117.87, 115.78, 114.81–113.39 (m), 104.36, 82.48, 74.89, 70.30, 65.54, 64.56, 60.92, 55.83, 51.12, 48.02, 47.85, 47.68, 47.51, 47.34, 47.17, 47.00. HRMS calcd for C₁₇H₂₂N₂O₈ + H⁺ (M + H)⁺: 383.1454, found: 383.1444.

4.4.10. General procedure for compounds **16a–16c**

To a suspension of compounds **15a–15c** (1 equiv.) in EtOH: H₂O (3:1), KOH was added, and the mixture was stirred at 80 °C for 4–6 h. The volatiles were evaporated *in vacuo*. The crude material was purified by preparative HPLC to obtain pure carboxylic acids **16a–16c**.

4.4.10.1. Methyl 3-O-((6-carboxy)1-methyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-2-ylmethyl)-methoxy)-β-D-galactopyranoside (16a). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **15a** (32.5 mg, 0.081 mmol) and KOH (13.2 mg, 0.24 mmol, 2.9 equiv.) in 4 mL EtOH: H₂O (3:1) for 6 h. Compound **16a** was obtained as an amorphous white solid in 52% yield (16.2 mg). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, D₂O) δ 7.93 (s, 1H, ArH), 7.82 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.53 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 1H, ArH), 5.13 (d, *J* = 14.6 Hz, 1H, CH₂C₉H₇N₂O₂), 5.01 (d, *J* = 14.6 Hz, 1H, CH₂C₉H₇N₂O₂), 4.32–4.26 (m, 1H, H-1), 4.17 (s, 1H, H-4), 3.79 (s, 3H, NCH₃), 3.77–3.67 (m, 2H, H-6a, H-6b), 3.65–3.61 (m, 2H, H-3, H-5), 3.50 (s, 3H, OCH₃). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, D₂O) δ 171.71, 151.83, 135.47, 133.14, 130.39 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz), 125.84, 114.98, 112.80, 103.53, 81.71, 74.78, 69.79, 65.28, 61.92, 60.75, 57.13, 30.56. HRMS calcd for C₁₇H₂₂N₂O₈ + H⁺ (M + H)⁺: 383.1454, found: 383.1444.

4.4.10.2. Methyl 3-O-((5-carboxy)1-methyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-2-ylmethyl)-methoxy)-β-D-galactopyranoside (16b). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **15b** (41.3 mg, 0.1 mmol) and KOH (15.4 mg, 0.27 mmol, 2.7 equiv.) in 4 mL EtOH: H₂O (3:1) for 4 h. Compound **16b** was obtained as an amorphous white solid in 56% yield (17 mg). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 8.18 (s, 1H, Ar–H), 7.94 (dd, *J* = 8.5, 1.6 Hz, 1H, Ar–sH), 7.67 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 1H, Ar–H), 5.05 (q, 2H, *J* = 13.2, 6.14 Hz, 2H, CH₂C₉H₇N₂O₂), 4.17 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1H, H-1), 4.14 (d, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 1H, H-4), 3.83–3.67 (m, 3H, H-2, H-6a, H-6b), 3.54 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.51 (m, 1H, H-5), 3.46 (dd, *J* = 9.6, 3.2 Hz, 1H, H-3). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, D₂O) δ 172.41, 151.74, 136.01, 132.99, 130.87, 126.13, 116.88, 111.39, 103.52, 81.65, 74.77, 69.76, 65.31, 62.01, 60.74, 57.13, 30.71. HRMS calcd for C₁₇H₂₂N₂O₈ + H⁺ (M + H)⁺: 383.1454, found: 383.1448.

4.4.10.3. Methyl 3-O-((5-carboxy)1H-benzo[d]imidazole-2-ylmethyl)-methoxy)-β-D-galactopyranoside (16c). Following the general method, the reaction was performed with **15c** (21.9 mg, 0.056 mmol) and KOH (10.1 mg, 0.18 mmol, 3 equiv.) in 4 mL EtOH: H₂O (3:1) for 6 h. Compound **16c** was obtained as an amorphous

white solid in 37% yield (7.6 mg). ^1H NMR (500 MHz, D_2O) δ 7.82 (s, 1H, ArH), 7.70 (dd, $J = 8.6, 1.5$ Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.38 (d, $J = 8.6$ Hz, 1H, ArH), 5.03 (d, $J = 14.8$ Hz, 1H, $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$), 4.91 (d, $J = 14.8$ Hz, 1H, $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$), 4.29 (d, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 1H, H-1), 4.15 (d, $J = 3.1$ Hz, 1H, H-4), 3.78–3.56 (m, 5H, H-2, H-3, H-5, H-6a, H-6b), 3.50 (s, 3H, OCH_3). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, D_2O) δ 168.74, 152.37, 135.15, 132.50, 129.26, 125.63, 115.56, 113.54, 103.50, 81.80, 74.74, 69.85, 65.24, 62.83, 60.76, 57.14. HRMS calcd for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_8 + \text{H}^+$ ($\text{M} + \text{H}$) $^+$: 369.1298, found: 369.1289.

4.4.11. 3,4-Dichlorophenyl 3-O-((5-methoxycarbonyl)1-methyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-2-ylmethyl)-1-thio- α -D-galactopyranoside (**18a**)

Compound **17** [17] (100 mg, 0.29 mmol), Compound **14a** (83.4 mg, 0.35 mmol, 1.2 equiv.), Bu_2SnO (80.3 mg, 0.32 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $n\text{-Bu}_4\text{NI}$ (270.7 mg, 0.73 mmol, 1.2 equiv.) were dissolved in 4.8 mL toluene: MeCN (5:1) in a 2–5 mL biotage microwave vial. The reaction was run at 120 °C for 1 h under normal absorption of the microwave. The volatiles were evaporated *in vacuo*. The mixture was purified with flash column chromatography (DCM: MeOH: 97: 3% to 95: 5%) followed by preparative HPLC to provide **18a** as a white amorphous solid (50.6 mg, 31% yield). ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 8.23 (s, 1H, ArH), 7.97 (dd, $J = 8.5, 1.6$ Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.73 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.71 (d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.49–7.42 (m, 2H, ArH), 5.70 (d, $J = 5.6$ Hz, 1H, H-1), 5.08 (q, $J = 13.6, 2.2$ Hz, 2H, $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$), 4.41 (q, $J = 10.1, 5.6$ Hz, 1H, H-2), 4.29 (t, $J = 6.2$ Hz, 1H, H-4), 4.26 (d, $J = 2.2$ Hz, 2H, H-5), 3.98 (s, 3H, CO_2CH_3), 3.97 (s, 3H, NCH_3), 3.79–3.62 (m, 3H, H-3, H-6a, H-6b). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 167.29, 144.52, 135.34, 132.90, 131.98, 131.19, 130.62, 130.15, 124.71, 123.30, 118.07, 111.89, 89.66, 79.57, 72.05, 67.49, 65.93, 63.10, 60.86, 51.19, 29.36. HRMS calcd for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{24}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_7\text{S} + \text{H}^+$ ($\text{M} + \text{H}$) $^+$: 543.0760, found: 543.0753.

4.4.12. 3,4-Dichlorophenyl 3-O-((5-methoxycarbonyl)1H-benzo[d]imidazole-2-ylmethyl)-1-thio- α -D-galactopyranoside (**18b**)

Compound **17** (305.5 mg, 0.90 mmol), Compound **14d** (350 mg, 1.08 mmol, 1.2 equiv.), Bu_2SnO (245.1 mg, 0.98 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) and $n\text{-Bu}_4\text{NI}$ (496 mg, 1.34 mmol, 1.5 equiv.) were dissolved in 12 mL toluene: MeCN (5:1) in a 10–20 mL biotage microwave vial. The reaction was run at 120 °C for 90 min under normal absorption of the microwave. The volatiles were evaporated *in vacuo*. The mixture was purified with flash column chromatography (DCM: MeOH: 95: 5% to 90: 10%) followed by preparative HPLC to provide **18b** as a white amorphous solid (166 mg, 34% yield). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 8.28 (s, 1H, ArH), 7.97 (dd, $J = 8.5, 1.2$ Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.75 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.63 (d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.54–7.40 (m, 2H, ArH), 5.73 (d, $J = 5.5$ Hz, 1H, H-1), 5.06 (q, $J = 14.1$ Hz, 2H, $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$), 4.47 (dt, $J = 9.9, 5.5$ Hz, 1H, H-2), 4.36–4.27 (m, 2H, H-4, H-5), 3.95 (s, 3H, CO_2CH_3), 3.87–3.66 (m, 3H, H-3, H-6a, H-6b). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 167.59, 135.34, 133.04, 132.10, 131.32, 130.78, 130.26, 124.31, 123.69, 89.57, 80.08, 72.08, 67.73, 66.14, 64.62, 60.94, 51.21. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_7\text{S} + \text{H}^+$ ($\text{M} + \text{H}$) $^+$: 529.0603, found: 529.0610.

4.4.13. 3,4-Dichlorophenyl 3-O-((5-carboxy)1-methyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazole-2-ylmethyl)-1-thio- α -D-galactopyranoside (**19a**)

Compound **18a** (23.3 mg, 0.042 mmol) and KOH (9.8 mg, 0.174 mmol, 4 equiv.) were dissolved in 4 mL EtOH: H_2O (3:1), and the reaction was run at 80 °C for 6 h until the TLC indicated the complete consumption of the starting material. The solvent was evaporated *in vacuo*, and compound **19a** was purified by preparative HPLC. White amorphous solid (7 mg, 31% yield). ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 8.26 (d, $J = 1.5$ Hz, 1H, ArH), 8.00 (dd, $J = 8.5, 1.6$ Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.74 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.71 (d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.50–7.41 (m, 2H, ArH), 5.70 (d, $J = 5.6$ Hz, 1H, H-1), 5.09 (q, $J = 13.3, 2.0$ Hz, 2H, $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$), 4.41 (dd, $J = 10.1, 5.6$ Hz, 1H, H-

2), 4.29 (t, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 2H, H-4), 4.26 (d, $J = 3.0$ Hz, 1H, H-5), 4.00 (s, 3H, NCH_3), 3.79–3.64 (m, 3H, H-3, H-6a, H-6b). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 168.92, 154.21, 144.29, 135.43 (d, $J = 18.1$ Hz), 132.91, 131.98, 131.20, 130.62, 130.15, 123.63, 117.87, 111.99, 89.66, 79.54, 72.06, 67.50, 65.94, 63.10, 60.87, 29.31. HRMS calcd for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_7\text{S} + \text{H}^+$ ($\text{M} + \text{H}$) $^+$: 529.0603, found: 529.0602.

4.4.14. 3,4-Dichlorophenyl 3-O-((5-carboxy)1H-benzo[d]imidazole-2-ylmethyl)-1-thio- α -D-galactopyranoside (**19b**)

Compound **18b** (106.8 mg, 0.20 mmol) and LiOH (30 mg, 1.25 mmol, 6 equiv.) were dissolved in 4 mL EtOH: H_2O (3:1), and the reaction was run at 80 °C overnight. The solvent was then evaporated *in vacuo*, and compound **19b** was purified by preparative HPLC. White amorphous solid (43.1 mg, 41% yield). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 8.18 (s, 1H, ArH), 7.87 (dd, $J = 8.5, 1.6$ Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.64 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.50 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.42–7.31 (m, 2H, ArH), 5.61 (d, $J = 5.6$ Hz, 1H, H-1), 4.94 (q, $J = 14.0$ Hz, 2H, $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$), 4.34 (dd, $J = 10.1, 5.6$ Hz, 1H, H-2), 4.24–4.17 (m, 2H, H-4, H-5), 3.71–3.57 (m, 3H, H-3, H-6a, H-6b). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 135.36, 133.04, 132.10, 131.32, 130.77, 130.26, 123.97, 89.57, 80.08, 72.08, 67.73, 66.14, 64.63, 60.95. HRMS calcd for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{20}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_7\text{S} + \text{H}^+$ ($\text{M} + \text{H}$) $^+$: 515.0447, found: 515.0451.

4.5. Molecular dynamics simulations

Molecular dynamics simulations were performed using the OPLS3 force field in Desmond implemented in Schrödinger Release 2020-1, using default settings except for the length of the simulation, and the use of light harmonic constraints (1 kcal mol $^{-1}$ Å $^{-2}$) on all stranded backbone atoms and the galactose O4 atom. To keep galectin-8N simulations stable, the coulombic cut-off radius had to be increased from the default 9 Å to 10 Å. Galectin-3 complexes were constructed based on the structure with the PDB code 5GZD, while galectin-8N complexes on the structure with the PDB code 7AEN, and the ligands were placed by the superposition of the corresponding galactose parts.

Accession codes

Protein Data Bank: 7AEN, 7ALS.

Declaration of competing interest

F.R.Z. is an employee of, and H.L. and U.J.N. are shareholders in Galecto Biotech AB, a company developing galectin inhibitors. The other authors have no conflicts to declare.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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